

Fear of Missing Out (FoMO): Determinant Of Travel Behavior Among Gen Z Tourists

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to analyze whether Fear of Missing Out influences the travel behavior of Gen Z tourists by conducting a close-ended survey through Google Forms to the 168 selected Gen Z tourists among the selected academic courses from Bulacan State University Malolos campus. The findings disclosed that moderate FoMO are experienced by the respondents were triggered by social media, peer influences, and trends. As these elements drive the travel interest, intensity of FoMO varies. On top of that, FoMO based sales promotion affects the travel behavior of Gen Z, although the impact varies, High-value promotions are more effective in influencing their decision. Furthermore, it was revealed that their travel decisions in terms of travel frequency, destinations and spending behavior are influenced by peer recommendations and financial

considerations, balancing both personal desires and peer pressure. The result shows, specifically the FoMO drivers; social media influence and trend awareness, molds their travel behavior. However, the effect varies, with some being influenced stronger than others. Finally, this study provides an insightful perspective on how Gen Z FoMO play a significant role in their travel behavior. This study will surely be a guide to tourism marketers and travel industry professionals on how they will cater the big portion of their market by allowing them to gain a fresh perspective on the mind of Gen Z when it comes to their travel behavior.

Introduction

Generation Z, or those who were born between the late 1990s and the early 2010s— travel is more than just a form of leisure but also a means of self-expression and social validation that is often driven by trend and experiences shared across the social media (Pricope Vancia et al., 2024). The central of this behavior is the Fear of Missing Out (FoMO) which was stated as a psychological state or the feeling of an enjoying experience that the person is not part of (Przybylski et al., 2013). This behavior is originally conceptualized by Dan Herman (2000) as an anxiety-driven behavioral tendency then later popularized by Patrick J. McGinnis in 2004, and since then, FoMo has been recognized as a social and psychological condition that is strongly related to the rise of the digital communication and online comparison (Good & Hyman, 2020; Rees, 2017).

Although the travel habits of Gen Z are receiving more and more attention from the academics— there's still a limited knowledge or understanding of how FoMO directly influences their travel behavior and motivations. In addition to this, there are still limited studies that focus on its impact on travel

choices, as previous studies have only mainly examined FoMO in relation to consumer habits, mental health, or social media. To address this knowledge gap, this study explores FoMO as a distinct psychological factor that shapes Gen Z's travel behavior, particularly, in the Philippines where few studies have explored it (Antonio et al., 2023).

Recent findings indicate that FoMO plays a role in influencing Gen Z travel behavior worldwide. Wijayanti (2023), have found out that post-pandemic Gen Z tourists in Indonesia, tend to or prefer authentic and outdoor experiences, and often choose destinations that are known and popularized on social media. Similarly, Antonio et al. (2023) showed that peer, friend, and family expectations have a significant effect and shapes the travel desires of Filipino Gen Z travelers. For these reasons, these findings support Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behavior (1991), which states that the social and psychological factors shape a person's intentions.

This framework suggests that feeling left out affects social expectations which leads people to select activities and places that are digitally significant and approved by peers and the internet.

However, despite the growing scholarly attention, there's still a lot to learn about how much FoMO directly affects Gen Z's travel intentions, destination choices, and spending behavior. Previous researchers have only primarily examined the relationship between FoMO and social media activity rather than its direct impact on travel decision making. For instance, Wijayanti (2024) examined how Gen Z tourists in Bali viewed FoMO, but was unable to measure its behavioral consequences, whereas Klook (2025) study has discovered social media to be a substantial influence without identifying FoMO as a separate idea. As a result, there are also still population and practical gaps as there isn't enough research that look at specific Gen Z groups in different cultural contexts or offer evidence-based suggestions for ethical FoMO-based tourism marketing.

The purpose of this study is to investigate how the Gen Z tourists' travel habits are influenced by their Fear of Missing Out (FoMO). Particularly, it examines how this behavior affects their travel motivations, destination preferences, spending habits, and frequency of travel. Ultimately, the goal of this study is to provide evidence-based insights that could assist the future tourists, Tourism Marketers, Tourism Agencies, organizations, and future researchers to create ethical, FoMO-aware strategies that appeal to Gen Z tourists and promote sustainable and responsible travel practices.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to answer the general problem: How may the influence of Fear of Missing Out (FoMO) on the travel behavior and marketing preferences of Generation Z tourists be analyzed?

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How may the demographic profile of the respondents be described in terms of:

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- 1.1 Age,
 - 1.2 Gender,
 - 1.3 Courses, and
 - 1.4 Most Recent Vacation Decision-Making
2. What FoMO Sales promotion strategies are utilized that are most appealing to Gen Z tourists?
 - 2.1 Discount,
 - 2.2 Coupons, and
 - 2.3 Buy-One-Get-One-Free
 3. How may the FoMO drivers among Gen Z tourists be assessed in terms of:
 - 3.1 Social media engagement,
 - 3.2 Peer influence,
 - 3.3 Trend awareness, and
 - 3.4 Desire for unique experiences
 4. How may the travel behavior of Gen Z tourists be analyzed in terms of:
 - 4.1 Travel frequency,
 - 4.2 Destination choices, and
 - 4.3 Spending behavior
 5. What is the effect of FoMO sales promotion strategies on the travel behavior of Generation Z?
 6. How do FoMO drivers affect the travel behavior of Generation Z?

Significance of the Study

This research provides valuable insights into how Fear of Missing Out (FoMO) influences the travel

behavior of Gen Z in the Philippines, addressing a knowledge gap about its direct impact on tourist decisions. The findings may help Gen Z tourists in understanding how digital pressure influences their travel decisions, as well as to provide tourism businesses, marketers, and travel agencies guidance in creating responsible and appealing strategies that are aligned in the interests of Gen Z. It may also support policymakers and cultural organizations in developing programs that promote cultural preservation and sustainable tourism. Moreover, the research contributes to the tourism literature by incorporating a modern psychological concept and serves as a foundation for future research on generational behavior and future trends in tourism.

Conceptual Framework

The Self Determination Theory, that was developed by Deci & Ryan (1985), emphasizes psychological needs and human motivation affects the behavior of individuals. The three key psychological needs are autonomy, competence, and relatedness which SDT used to explain human motivation.

Autonomy is wanting to be in control and make your own decisions while competence is the desire to feel good in what you do and to be effective in what one does, and relatedness which refers to the need for connection with others and to feel that you belong. If these needs are met, an individual may achieve intrinsic motivation and psychological well-being. On the other hand, when these needs are not fulfilled, a person may engage in activities motivated by external factors or seek validation from others (Deci & Ryan, 2000).

SDT serves as the main theoretical framework used in this study in explaining how FoMO influences the travel behavior of Gen Z tourists. People engage in activities not only for inner fulfillment but also to avoid peer pressure or maintain connections with others. This feeling is identified as a controlled or extrinsic form of motivation, as scrolling through social media frequently reveals the travel experiences of others, which causes an external desire to engage in common things to satisfy their need for relatedness. Moreover, the need for autonomy may motivate tourists to seek personal experiences that reflect their identity, while the need

for competence may be achieved in exploring new destinations and showing accomplishments that express confidence and social worth.

SDT is the main theory used for this study as it integrates both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, providing a more thorough explanation of FoMO than any other psychological theories. It discusses how the travel decisions and preferences of Gen Z tourists are influenced by internal psychological needs and external influences like social media pressure. Visiting “instagram worthy” places, engaging in popular travel trends, or planning travel that are similar to their peers’ experiences, are some examples of motivations that ultimately affect different travel behavior.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Figure 1 presents an IV-DV model to assess the cause-and-effect between FoMO-based sales promotion strategies and FoMO drives (independent variables) and what influence it may have on Gen Z tourists’ travel behavior (dependent variables).

The FoMO-based sales promotion that could trigger a sense of urgency and peer comparison, and the FoMO drivers on social media, peer influence, trend awareness, and the desire for unique experiences might heighten the chance of Gen Z tourists engaging in travel. The effect might predict more impulsive travel decisions, affecting destination choices, spending habits, and travel frequency that is motivated by a desire to avoid feeling left out on what is happening on social media.

Review of Related Literatures

Fear Of Missing Out (FoMO)

Generation Z was referred to by Zeva et al. (2023) as individuals who are highly prone to the feeling of FoMO. They also described them as a group that is constantly updated to the emerging trends. In accordance with this definition, it emphasizes that this group is prone to feeling of missing out as they always follow the trends to always be updated and belong to the society. Thus, being informed makes them more sensitive, specifically when they cannot join other people having fun.

Consequently, according to the findings of Hayran & Gürhan-Cali (2022), it was stated that young adults often feel regrets when they miss out on opportunities. Likewise, they also feel anxiety if they do not participate in certain events or any social interactions (Wolniewicz et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018; Li et al., 2020). In this regard, Neumann (2020) noted that if they are affected by these feelings they will view their current experiences as less satisfying compared to what they missed. Additionally, the temporary disconnection can trigger their anxiety and distress, such situations can lead to feelings of restlessness, fear, and worry that it will negatively impact their relationship with others (Perrone, 2016; Çopuroğlu, 2021). This literature highlights how people often feel upset or anxious whenever they miss out on events or activities because they think that what they're doing is not as fun as the experience they missed out on. Also, missed out experiences make them feel like they will lose touch with others causing them to be more uneasy and anxious.

Travel FoMO

It was defined by Zaman et al. (2022), as a feeling of anxiety that arises from the fear that they will miss out on travel experiences, particularly if the one traveling is your peer or family. This definition was supported by the findings of Wojcieszak-Zbierska (2023), stating that what the tourist felt shapes their motivations and travel planning. Similarly, Boley and Woosnam (2021) argue that being left out strongly influences the tourist destination choices and overall travel behavior. Thus, this results in a situation that was found by Zaman (2024) that many tourists plan trips primarily to avoid missing unique or culturally enriching experiences. In accordance with the findings, it shows that the feeling of travel FoMO affects where or when a tourist will go, and they will choose a place that will ensure they won't miss any special or memorable experiences that the others have.

This phenomenon was associated by Abel and Buff (2016) with the emotional distress that the tourist felt when they were being deprived of vacation opportunities. In accordance with this,

Scheinfield & Voorhees (2022) stated that an individual who is always concerned about other people's opinions are more likely to “break routines” where they visit places that reflect their identity and a place that will bring them joy. Similarly, these kinds of tourists often travel to a distinct and meaningful destination to avoid missing out on any extraordinary cultural encounters (Wojcieszak-Zbierska, 2023). This research indicates that Travel FoMO happens when people feel upset when they miss out on their chance to take a trip. They also care about what others think of them, making them pick places that match their personality, unique destination, and will make them experience cultural moments so that they do not feel left out of society.

Social Media Influence on FoMO

According to the research of Cayubit (2018) with the title of “Fear of missing out and its link with social media and problematic Internet use among Filipinos” it is mentioned that the rise of Fear of missing out was driven by the rapid growth of internet and social media —this is their fear of being disconnected to the online world. In relation to this, another findings of Mohann & Shekhar (2021)

highlighted that the youth's too much engagement to social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and Snapchat, creates a feeling of exclusion. These online spaces encourage users to share their achievements, experiences, and lifestyles that may trigger constant comparison and competitiveness (Shruti, Anita, & Binita, 2025). According to the stated findings, FoMO is such a powerful factor to Gen Z since they spend a lot of time online they are constantly exposed to other people's travels, achievements, and exciting experiences through post. Seeing those updates creates a pressure to keep up or do something equally which influences their travel decisions. Additionally, understanding how social media triggers such emotion helps us to see why Gen Z may choose to travel frequently, visit trendy destinations, or for the marketers to take advantage of FoMO-based promotions. It's also shaped by the emotional and psychological impact of being connected to online.

Furthermore, too much exposure to social media can lead to feelings of loneliness, anxiety, and depression (Hattingh et al., 2022). This was further explained by Patria and Rahtomo (2020) in their

findings about how today's youth show such a strong dependency on smartphones, constantly checking to stay informed because missing out on updates can trigger anxiety and a sense of social exclusion.

Gen Z Travel Behavior and Characteristics

Zeva et. al describes the Gen Z as “updated with technology” and “Trend-conscious” individuals. This generation is driven by connectivity and rapid digital development, marking them the first generation to be entirely digital (Phino & Gomes, 2023). According to Monaco (2018); R. Egger et al. (2016) being born in a digitally connected environment, they often share their travel experiences with their friends online. Richards (2015) mentioned that it differs from older generations as Gen Z prefers personalized and engaging travel experiences, usually caused by digital contents, influencers and online reviews. This explains why when it comes to travel, Gen Z are affected the most. This is because they are exposed to technology growing up, this is why they rely on online content when they make decisions like “Where to travel, what activities to try, and which experiences are worthy”.

Another similar study conducted by Wigmore (2025) mentioned that the Gen Z are influenced by their interest for adventure and self-discovery, emphasizing their preference in traveling alone. Additionally, Gomez et al (2025) said that Gen Z's desire for authenticity and social media engagement affects the local communities and destination choices, especially in urban areas. Pricope Vancia et al. (2023) said that their spending habits benefit industries like accommodation, food & beverages and tourism. These studies show how Gen Z's motivation and behavior shapes their ways of travel and how they react to FoMO based sales promotions. Their desire for new experiences makes them more likely to respond as they see other people do something that intrigues them. Knowing the factors that influence their travel behavior will help boost the tourism industry by realizing the real-world impact of Gen Z travel behavior. This backs-up the importance of learning the impact of FoMO on travel behavior, not just for Gen Z, but for the tourism sectors to understand the growing market of Gen Z.

Peer Influence on Travel Decisions

FoMO in relation to peers according to Euromonitor (2011) that was cited by Saavedra & Bautista (2020) is that it influences Gen Z's travel behavior, because they are a generation that rely on peers for emotional validation and decision-making. Additionally, Satriawan et al. (2022) have similar findings, they also observed that one of the factors that affect this young adults behavior is peer influence. This observation was further explained by Hodkinson (2016) in his literature entitled "Fear of missing out" (FoMO) marketing appeals: "A conceptual model", stating that the travel experiences of their friends often trigger the emotion of being left out—these motivate them to pursue similar experiences as the others. In accordance with these findings, it shows how the influence of their peers became an important factor in understanding the effect of FoMO on their travel behavior. An exposure to their friends' travel experiences motivates them to plan trips, choose destinations, and engage in the same activities to fulfill their social and emotional needs.

Furthermore, there is a comparable result of Varga and Gabor (2021) in Romania that found out how social networks allow its users to observe the lifestyles of their peers—this observation affects their travel preferences. It was also shown that even how much it causes pressure to the young adults they still take their peers' recommendations since they act as their trusted sources of information. This is proven by Zaman (2024) stating that their personal connections and peer experiences will inspire people to visit the same locations and share comparable travel moments with others. Correspondingly, since they rely on their peers and compare experiences—Harahap et al. (2024) also provide findings about how tourists rely on feedback from other people who have previously visited the destinations. In relation to this study, social media is being considered as the primary channel that FoMO operates because it gives constant exposure to peers' travel activities, trends, and shared experiences. This affects both the young adults' destination choices and the way they engage in travel. It also emphasizes the combined effect of the peer influence and internet interactions on their travel intentions, preferences, and behaviors.

Related Studies

Antecedents and Consequences of FoMO in Tourism

Concerning the mental health of social media use among teenagers, experts have recently taken notice of FoMO (Balta et al., 2020). According to early studies on the prevalence of such emotion, over 75% of youth reported having experienced the phenomenon (Adams et al., 2017).

Kurniawan & Susilo (2024) performed a systematic analysis of previous research on the causes and consequences of FoMO in tourism by analysing 56 English-language papers from the Scopus database using the PRISMA standards. The review shows that perceived loneliness, reference groups, and electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) are the main factors that influence FoMO in the travel industry. The three findings are: the intention to search for travel information, the intention to visit destinations, and overall positive well-being.

According to the report, these results can be used as a marketing tactic by tourist businesses to encourage more travel and new experiences. Overall, these insights show how FOMO works as a both psychological motivator and behavioral determinant, making it an important factor in order to understand more the travel behavior and motivations of Gen Z tourists.

FoMO and the Gen Z Travel Market

Gen Z is quickly becoming a disruptive force in the travel and hospitality sectors, not only because of their increasing purchasing power but also because of their unique tastes and habits but also because of their unique tastes and habits. Their tendency for immersive, socially shareable, and real experiences is changing both business tactics and customer expectations. For organizations hoping to draw in and keep this powerful group, it is critical to comprehend this generation's attitude, especially their FoMO-driven driver (Durge, S., Poojary, C. K., Kulkarni, P., & Pimplapure, V. 2025).

This related study of Durge, Poojary, Kulkarni, & Pimplapure (2025), examines how travel

and spending habits in the travel and hospitality sectors are impacted by this feeling. Their study presents the idea of the "Gen Z FoMO Economy," illustrating how their purchasing decisions are influenced by this sense of urgency. It also looks at how companies may utilize FoMO-based tactics to draw in Gen Z tourists, improve brand loyalty, and forge closer bonds with clients in a competitive industry. These studies show and demonstrate Gen Z's desire to stay connected, relevant, and include driving both their spending patterns and travel behavior. Moreover, this reveals how tourism businesses use FoMO-based strategies like limited offers and shareable contents to attract these Gen Z travelers. All in all, this result clearly supports the idea of how FoMO does not only motivate the Gen Z's travel behavior but it also drives the competitiveness in the tourism market.

Social Media, FoMO, and Travel Decision

Social media has been integrated to the whole lives of Gen Z that it significantly impacts how they plan their journey in this digital era. People who are constantly exposed to the experiences of other people on the internet often compare their own lives

on the internet often compare their own lives with social comparison and social exclusion. Specifically, in the tourism context, the sense of being excluded motivates people to look for similar or even better experiences.

A similar study of Donghee Kim & Patchawaran Wongsu (2025) tested how social media causes social comparison and perceived exclusion affects travel plans. The researchers found through quantitative analysis of 253 respondents that excessive social media use increases the feeling of separation, where the social comparison influences both FoMO and desire to travel. This study backs up the idea that travel decisions are influenced psychologically driven by FoMO, especially among the Gen Z who grew up in the digital age.

The Digital Self and FoMO in Tourism Experiences

As the world starts to shift to digital and technology, social media has grown to more than just a showcase of travel photography, it has also changed how people see and present themselves. According to Belk (2016), the new idea of the “digital extended

self”, people view their online identity as a vital component that makes who they are. However, due to FoMO, these users might share more than their travel experiences (Souza et al., 2025). This combination suggests that these tourists share their travel experiences to stabilize their digital identities, reduce social exclusion and preserve memories.

Another related study by Barbosa, Guimarães, and Souza (2025), examines how the Digital Extended Self (DES) and Fear of Missing Out (FoMO) molds individual’s motivation and behavior when they share their travel experiences on the internet often compare their own lives with what online. The findings of this study discovered that FoMO significantly affects both the frequency and motivations for sharing, while DES affects only the underlying reasons relevant to self-expression. This study shows how FoMO drives digital engagement in travel contexts. Given the strong reliance of Gen Z on their social media identity and expressions, the result backs up the notion that FoMO meaningfully contribute to their travel behavior.

Research Methodology

Methods and Techniques of the Study

Quantitative techniques were used to examine the connection between Gen Z travel behavior and FoMO. A correlational research design was used in this study to determine the relationship between the Fear of Missing Out (FoMO) and the travel behavior of Gen Z tourists. Sukardi (2018) stated that in this approach the researchers do not manipulate the variables, instead they analyze if there is a relationship between variables and the level of the relationship occurs.

Furthermore, in order to gather data from the Gen Z respondents, a survey questionnaire through Google Form was used. This study's quantitative survey approach is appropriate as it allows for the systematic collection and statistical analysis of measurable information, allowing the researchers to objectively investigate the connection between Generation Z tourists' travel habits and their Fear of Missing Out (FoMO). This method also allows the researchers to determine the ways in which FoMO affects travel frequency, impulsive reservations, destination selection, trip duration, and social-sharing

behaviors. Similarly, the study of V. H. Nguyen. et al. (2021) uses statistical methods (reliability, validity, and demographic/frequency analysis), pre-testing, purposive sampling, and a quantitative survey among Gen Z— thus, showing the usefulness of survey tools and statistical techniques in revealing the relationship between Gen Z travel desires and concepts such as social media usage.

Participants of the Study

The respondents will be those who have engaged in any travel activities and experienced FoMO. Conducting the study in the same institution allows the researchers to easily reach the respondents. Furthermore, according to the official website of Bulacan State University, the total population of the students based on their annual report for the year 2023-2024 is 26,365. With reference to this, the estimated total population of BulSU students for the year 2025-2026 is about 30,000, consisting of 14 colleges. However, the researchers limit their study to 9 selected courses of BulSU: Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management (BSTM), Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management (BSHM), Bachelor of Science in Social Work (BSSW), Bachelor of Science

in Psychology (BSP), Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship (BSE), Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA), Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Marketing Management (BSBA-MM), Bachelor of Arts in Broadcasting (BAB), and Bachelor of Arts in Journalism (BAJ).

Selected colleges and reasons for inclusion

1. CHTM (BS Tourism Management and BS Hospitality Management) aligns with the tourism context of the study. These students are highly engaged in travel, tourism, and hospitality activities because their curriculum includes travel psychology, marketing, and destination management. Hence, they possess firsthand experience in travel planning and behavior.

2. CSSP (BS Psychology and BS Social Work) has a strong foundation in understanding human behavior, psychology, and its social influence. They can provide insight into how emotional triggers, social comparison, and digital exposure influence human decision-making, making it relevant to social psychology and consumer behavior courses.

Therefore, these students have insights about the emotional and social aspect of being left out and its impact on travel behavior.

3. CBEA (BS Business Administration, BS Business Administration Major in Marketing and BS Entrepreneurship) are familiar with marketing, consumer behavior, and decision-making processes that are closely related to the behaviors motivated by exclusion. As well as on the effects of social influence, pure comparison, and digital trends.

4. CAL (BA Broadcasting and BA Journalism) are creative, expressive, artistic, and socially aware. They study culture, media, and communication. Therefore, their engagement with media, and creative platforms aligns with the research focus on the feeling of missing out and its effect on travel behavior.

In order to determine the size of the sample, a purposive sampling method will be used. According to the study by memon et al. (2025) entitled Purposive Sampling: A Review and Guidelines for Quantitative Research, cited from Aguinis (2025) that purposive sampling is where the researchers select

the respondents based on their judgement. This non-probability sampling method is based on the criteria that provide the most informative insights and are relevant to the research's objectives (Palinkas et al., 2015; Andrade, 2021; Saunders et al., 2023).

Accordingly, the researchers selected the respondents in BulSU who met the criteria relevant to the study. An online survey through Google Forms will be distributed to these qualified respondents using social media platforms. Considering this, the target number of respondents for the survey is 200 Gen Z students. However, given that the study will use purposive sampling, the total number of respondents may vary depending on the respondents' eligibility for the criteria set by the researcher.

Nevertheless, it was also acknowledged by Memon et al. (2025), that using this type of sampling will limit the generalizability of the study's finding, as the researchers will base it on their judgement rather than random selection. Hence, the researchers also recognized that the results of the findings do not represent the entire population of BulSU students because the method used in this study relies on the

researchers' criteria. In using purposive sampling and online surveys, it will result in potential biases and limitations that may influence the validity, reliability, and generalizability of the research findings. Moreover, online surveys through Google forms can result in response bias, where the respondents provide socially desirable answers rather than their accurate and truthful responses. Additionally, a nonresponse bias may also occur if the respondents failed to complete or submit the survey. Hence, the survey's questions will be modified into required responses to ensure complete data collection.

Furthermore, to mitigate these challenges, a selection criterion was clearly defined, ensuring to include only those relevant to the study. The researchers also ensure the anonymity and confidentiality of the data for a more honest response and reduce social desirability bias. In addition the increase of diversity and population by getting respondents from 9 different courses from BulSU will help to balance the potential biases and strengthen the validity of the findings. Whereas, even if it limits generalizability, this method will be

applied to ensure that the respondents were in line with the study's objectives of determining how FoMO influences the travel behavior among Gen Z tourists.

Research Instrument

The research instrument used in this study was an online survey consisting of self-made questions designed to collect quantitative data on the effect of Fear of Missing Out (FoMO) on the travel behavior of Gen Z tourists.

The researcher will be using Google Forms to collect data and answers that consist of 30 close-ended questions divided into five (5) sections: (1) Data Privacy & Qualifications (2) Demographic Profile, (2) FoMO Based Sales Promotion Strategies, (3) Travel Behavior, (4) FoMO Drivers, and (5) Ending Message

The researcher will be using a five point Likert scale for the questionnaire that ranges from (5) Always. (4) Often, (3) Sometimes, (2) Rarely, and (1) Never to measure how frequently or strongly the respondents will agree with each statement. The Data

analysis included descriptive statistics using the weighted mean to determine levels of agreement, frequency and percentage to describe demographic characteristics, and correlation analysis to examine the relationship between FoMO and travel behavior.

To ensure the Reliability and Validity of our research instrument we subjected our instrument to Three Expert Validations to check the Questionnaire Contents: Validity, Clarity, Relevant and Alignment within our objective.

Ethical Consideration

In the agreement of the respondents to answer researcher online surveys the researcher will remember the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (R.A. 10173), that all responses will be kept confidential and would only be used for research purposes. No personal information was shared without consent, and all data was kept securely to ensure privacy and protection.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data for this study will be collected from Gen Z students studying at Bulacan State

University-Main Campus. The respondents will be selected from nine courses who will meet the criteria set by the researchers. An online survey questionnaire will be disseminated using Facebook, Messenger, and Instagram and will be administered through Google Forms. These platforms were selected because Gen Z often uses them, and they allow the researchers to reach a wide range of possible respondents within the university.

The data collection will be carried out approximately for a one-week period. Throughout the whole week, the recruitment message and survey link will be disseminated by the researchers through social media posts and official student group chats. The message will include a brief introduction of the study, its objective, and a statement stating that taking part is voluntary and all responses will be kept strictly confidential.

The online survey will consist of thirty (30) close-ended questions categorized into five (5) sections: (1) Data Privacy & Qualifications (2) Demographic Profile, (2) FoMO Based Sales

Promotion Strategies, (3) Travel Behavior, (4) FoMO Drivers, and (5) Ending Message. All survey items will be set as required in Google Forms to avoid missing or incomplete data. After the data collection period, the researchers will thoroughly review all the responses for completeness before organizing, encoding, and tabulating the data for statistical analysis to determine how FoMO influences the travel behavior of Gen Z students of Bulacan State University- Malolos Campus.

Data Processing and Statistical Treatment

The statistical methods used to examine the data collected from the respondents will be presented in this segment. Using the Jamovi 2.7. 12, the analyses were performed. These statistical treatments were utilized based on the nature of the research questions, level of measurement of the variables and the research objectives, which aim to determine the effect of FoMO based sales promotion and FoMO drivers on Gen Z's travel behavior.

Descriptive Statistics were used to sum up the demographic profile of the respondents, FoMO

based sales promotion strategies, FoMO drivers, and travel behavior. These include;

Frequency and Percentage is used to categorize the variables such as age, gender, college course, and most recent vacation decision-making.

Weighted mean and Standard Deviation is used for measurable items that use Likert-scale such as FoMO based sales promotion strategies, FoMO drivers, and travel behavior.

Verbal Interpretation was applied to interpret the level of agreement of the respondents using the Five-point Likert scale below;

Interval	Scale	Description
4.20 – 5.00	5	Always
3.40 – 4.19	4	Often
2.60 – 3.39	3	Sometimes
1.80 – 2.59	2	Rarely
1.00 – 1.79	1	Never

Inferential Statistics. To address the effects of FoMO on Gen Z travel behavior, the study used Multiple Regression Analysis.

Multiple Regression Analysis. was used to examine the effect of FoMO based sales promotion strategies (Discounts, Coupons, Buy-One-Get-One-Free) on the travel behavior dimensions of Gen Z (Travel Frequency, Destination Choices, Spending Behavior). Additionally, it assesses the effect of FoMO Drivers (Social Media Engagement, Peer Influence, Trend Awareness, Desire for New Experiences) on their travel behavior.

The regression output included:

Unstandardized Coefficients (B) and standard errors to explain the raw effect of each predictor.

- **Standardized coefficients (β)** to evaluate the relative contribution of each predictor
- **t-values and p-values** to discover the statistical significance at $\alpha = 0.05$.
- **Standardized estimates** were used in Jamovi for reporting β values.

Results

The demographic profile of the 168 Gen Z respondents. It was revealed in the result that the majority respondents were aged 19 to 21, with a total of 75% of the sample. Additionally, in terms of gender distribution, the larger part of the respondents with 61.9% are females. Furthermore, the respondents are from 9 courses with Hospitality (14.3%) and Tourism (17.9%) students representing a large proportion with a total of 32.2%. Moreover, in recent travel decision-making, most respondents answered that their travel choices were influenced by family decisions (41.7%), followed by peers (28%), and social media exposure (14.9%). The respondents

represent young, digitally active, and easily influenced by social media platforms. The findings reveal that Gen Z's travel behaviors are greatly modeled by their family and social media influences. Most of the respondents are in the age of 19-21, this explains why family has the biggest impact as they still rely on their family.

With this, peers who share their experiences on social media also influence their travel behavior which creates the fear of missing out. High number of female and Tourism/Hospitality students recommends greater exposure to social media and travel-related content, making them more responsive to trends and comparison. Even though social media is third on the ranking, it still activates interest and FoMO by exhibiting popular destinations. Overall, Gen Z travel decisions are led by family guidance, peer influence, and social media exposure, these factors are closely tied to FoMO behavior.

Frequency and Percentage Distribution on the Profile of the Respondents

Profile	Categories	Frequency	%
Age	17 years old	2	1.2
	18 years old	20	11.9
	19 years old	46	27.4
	20 years old	47	28
	21 years old	33	19.6

	22 years old	18	10.7
	23 years old	2	1.2
Gender	Male	64	38.1
	Female	104	61.9
College Courses	BSTM	30	17.9
	BSHM	24	14.3
	BSSW	17	10.1
	BSP	21	12.5
	BSE	18	10.7
	BSBA	15	8.9
	BAB	20	11.9
	BAJ	20	11.9
	BSBA-MM	3	1.8
Most Recent Travel Decision-Making	I saw it on social media	25	14.9
	My family decided	70	41.7
	My friends decided	47	28
	I chose it because of my own curiosity	18	10.7
	I chose it because it was the most suitable place for my budget	8	4.8
		<i>n = 168</i>	100

FoMO Sales Promotion Strategies Appealing to Gen Z Tourists

This section presents the respondents' assessments of different FoMO-driven sales promotion strategies and identifies which are most effective to Generation Z tourists. The analysis focuses on the commonly used promotional strategies

such as Discounts, Coupons, and Buy-One-Get-One-Free offers. These methods are known to activate determination, selectiveness, and decision-making among Generation Z consumers.

FoMO Sales Promotion Strategies on Discounts

The weighted mean, standard deviation, and verbal interpretation of FoMO Sales Promotion Strategies on Discounts as perceived by Generation Z tourists. The Discounts received an “Often” interpretation with the weighted mean of 3.65 and a standard deviation of 1.12. This shows that the respondents have a positive response to discount promotions, particularly during limited time offers.

This shows that the strategies in terms of discount have influenced their travel behavior. Furthermore, it aligns with recent studies showing that discounts and time-limited deals heighten excitement and create urgency among young consumers, encouraging quicker travel decisions (Przybylski et al., 2020; Alalwan, 2022). This research supports that FoMO enhances responsiveness to online promotional strategies, making Gen Z more inclined to act when they

perceive exclusive or rare offers. The Generation Z are price-conscious thus discount-based promotions can effectively stimulate travel bookings. Travel agencies and tourism establishments may maximize engagement by promoting time-limited discount strategies.

FoMO Sales Promotion Strategies on Coupons

The weighted mean, standard deviation, and verbal interpretation of FoMO Sales Promotion Strategies on Coupons among Generation Z tourists indicate that respondents “Sometimes” respond to coupon-based promotions, with an overall weighted mean of 3.36 and a standard deviation of 1.17. This suggests that coupons have a moderate influence on their travel decision. As supported by recent studies, coupon-based promotions can encourage travel interest, especially when offered online, but they tend to create a moderate sense of urgency compared to discounts (Bai et al., 2021). A possible reason for moderate rating is that Gen Z prefers a rapid, hassle-free transaction. If a coupon requires multiple steps or feels less rewarding than direct discounts, therefore the redemption on these coupons will decrease. Coupons may still be effective if it is

applied at checkout or automatically integrated into booking platforms. FoMO plays a role in motivating young consumers to act, but the effect of coupons is generally less intense than other FoMO-driven promotional strategies.

FoMO Sales Promotion Strategies on Buy-1-Get-1-Free

The weighted mean, standard deviation, and verbal interpretation of FoMO Sales Promotion Strategies on Buy-One-Get-One-Free (B1G1F) promotions received the highest interpretation of “Often” with a weighted mean of 3.84 and a standard deviation of 1.06. This suggests that B1G1F promotions are a strong motivator for Generation Z tourists, effectively encouraging engagement and travel-related decision-making. Overall, the results indicate that B1G1F promotions are more influential than coupons and even slightly more impactful than standard discounts in motivating Gen Z tourists. A recent study of Bai et al. (2021) supports how the B1G1F and value-driven promotions can influence the Gen Z interest and urgency. In relation to this, it appeals both their financial savings and their fear of missing out, which drives them to make a decision

quickly and engage more with travel opportunities (Przybylski et al., 2020; Alalwan, 2022). These kinds of deals will encourage them to book trips more than the coupons or regular discounts. Offering B1G1F can grab their attention, and make them act quickly which leads to the increased bookings.

Summary of Ratings on the FoMO Sales Promotion Strategies

Gen Z respondents strongly attracted to the Buy-One-Get-One-Free (B1G1F), these promotions received the highest overall weighted mean of 3.84, followed by Discounts at 3.65—both interpreted as “Often”, which means that these promotion triggers the excitement and urgency of the customers. On the other hand, Coupons at 3.36 that are interpreted only as “Sometimes”. The results of the findings suggest that among the three promotional strategies, the most appealing to the tourist is the B1G1F deals, likely because of the combination of its value and the urgency associated with the limited time offers. Overall, the summary shows that B1G1F and discounts strategies are more effective in triggering their FoMO as this offers tangible benefits and is time-limited. Which means that those marketers who

are aiming to engage with this demographic should prioritize value-oriented and urgent promotional offers to maximize the travel engagement and booking behavior of the target market.

FoMO Drivers among Gen Z Tourists

This section presents the drivers of Generation Z tourists based on the influence of Fear of Missing Out (FoMO). This part examines their FoMO-driven engagement in terms of social media involvement, peer influence, trend awareness, and their desire to seek unique and memorable travel experiences.

FoMO Drivers among Gen Z Tourists in terms of Social Media Engagement

The FoMO drivers in terms of social media engagement obtained an overall weighted mean of 2.96, interpreted as “Sometimes.”. This suggests that while social media plays a role in shaping travel behavior, it does not strongly drive constant engagement among respondents. Overall, Generation Z tourists use social media selectively, primarily to observe trends or share experiences, rather than as a major source of travel-related anxiety. Studies show

social media influences travel inspiration and decision-making, but its impact varies by personality and digital habits (Przybylski et al., 2020). While some experience FoMO and post frequently, others engage more moderately. Instead of feeling compelled to visit, it would simply add to their travel inspiration list without letting it dictate plans.

FoMO Drivers among Gen Z Tourists in terms of Peer Influence

FoMO drivers in terms of peer influence obtained an overall weighted mean of 2.84, interpreted as “Sometimes.” This indicates that peer influence moderately affects travel behavior, suggesting that while respondents consider their friends’ activities when planning trips, it is not a constant or overwhelming factor. These findings suggest Gen Z tourists are influenced by peers as a reference, not to be pressured, in travel decisions. Peer engagement helps maintain social connections but doesn’t strongly dictate behavior. Studies show peer influence plays a moderate role, with its impact varying based on individual preferences and social confidence (Bai et al., 2021). Seeing friends post a destination, they casually add it to their travel list

without compulsion, enjoying the connection but not letting it pressure them to come along.

FoMO Drivers among Gen Z Tourists in terms of Trend Awareness

FoMO drivers in terms of trend awareness obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.10, interpreted as “Sometimes.” This suggests that while trends and popular destinations influence travel decisions, they do so only moderately, and respondents do not consistently rely on trending information to plan trips. Overall, these findings suggest that Generation Z tourists are selectively guided by trends, using social media and influencer content as inspiration rather than as a primary driver of their travel behavior. Recent studies indicate that trend awareness and social media influence can guide travel planning among young tourists, but their impact varies depending on personal preferences and the perceived relevance of trends (Goh & Okumus, 2020). that an influencer's post about a new travel destination, which sparks curiosity. However, instead of booking a trip right away, recognizing that trends are a source of ideas, but not the main factor in shaping their travel plans, business and marketers

have an idea how they can influence and attract tourists by using trends in social media.

FoMO Drivers among Gen Z Tourists in terms of Desire for Unique Experiences

FoMO drivers in terms of desire for unique experiences obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.06, interpreted as “Sometimes.” It suggests that the respondents moderately consider the need to join a unique or exclusive experience when making a travel decision, but it is not considered a driving factor. Generally, these findings imply that Gen Z might value memorable and unique experiences; they are not strongly influenced by fear of missing out. That it suggests that they have a moderate and deliberate approach to experiential travel;, studies have shown that young tourists increasingly seek unique and authentic experiences, but the intensity of FoMO varies depending on personality trait and social context (Przybylski et al., 2020; Bai et al., 2021). This shows that Gen Z's tend to value more on emotional satisfaction rather than social validation, as their experiences are chosen based on their preferences and not on social pressure. This suggests

that the tourism business should focus on unique and immersive experiences that connect with young tourists' personal interests. While memorable experiences are valued, a more thoughtful and targeted approach is likely to be more effective in appealing to this generation.

Summary of Ratings on the FoMO Drivers among Gen Z Tourists

The summary of rating of FoMO drivers among Gen Z tourists indicates that all four indicators; social media engagement, peer influence, trend awareness and desire for unique experiences, were assessed as “Sometimes” trend awareness have the highest weighted mean of 3.10, indicating the occasional influence on travel decision. The desire for unique experiences at 3.06 shows a moderate consideration of adventurous trips, while social media engagement at 2.96 and peer influence at 2.84 show a moderate result as well. A non-overwhelming impact on travel behavior. In summary, the results show that Gen Z tourists are engaged selectively with FoMO-driven factors, using social media, peer input, and trends as checklists rather than constant drivers on decision making in travel. This implies that FoMO

might have existed among Gen Z tourists, but it expressed fairly and does not—dominate in travel behavior. These insights help businesses focus on offering unique experiences that are aligned with the Gen Z’s interests, rather than pushing constant trend-driven promotions, allowing them to engage more effectively.

Travel Behavior of Generation Z Tourists

This part of the research presents the travel behavior of Generation Z tourists. This was done by analyzing how frequent they travel, what are the types of destinations they prefer, and their spending patterns during trips. Understanding these behaviors provides insight into FoMO-based sales promotions and travel motivation.

Travel Behavior of Generation Z Tourists in terms of Travel Frequency

The travel behavior of Generation Z tourists in terms of travel frequency is interpreted as “Always” with an overall weighted mean of 4.20 and standard deviation of 0.92. These results suggest that their travel frequency is strongly based on their social interaction, peer influence, and shared experiences. It also highlighted that for them it is not just a

recreational activity but also to be able to connect with other people. These findings above are supported by a recent study of Goh & Okumus (2020), that show how they are driven by the society, they value shared experiences, and peer recommendations which influences their travel behavior. Additionally, there were other findings of Sánchez-Cañizares et al. (2021) where they proved that social influence can predict the young adults' travel engagement, especially when their decisions are influenced by their friends or online communities. Overall, the results of these findings highlighted how their travel frequency is closely tied to their social interaction, peer endorsement, and opportunities for experiences. The data that was presented above suggested that their travel behavior is not simply about exploring new destinations for leisure, but it is strongly influenced by social factors. Additionally, the more these factors are combined into these travel offerings, the more likely they will engage with these travel options.

Travel Behavior of Generation Z Tourists in terms of Destination Choices

The travel behavior of Generation Z tourists in terms of destination choices have an overall weighted mean of 3.98 and a standard deviation of 0.92 that is verbally interpreted as “Often.” This indicates that they strongly considered various factors before deciding on a travel destination. Overall, the results above indicate that when they choose where to travel they always balance comfort, practicality, and social influence. These findings support earlier studies stating that in terms of selecting destinations, the young adults prioritize convenience, accommodation quality, and the recommendations from others (Bui & Kiatkawsin, 2020; Rahman et al., 2022). It proves that their decisions are influenced by a combination of practicality, comfort and social influence preferring a more convenient, quality accommodation and unique social experiences. Showing that the peer recommendations and the influence of social media have an impact in their travel decision making, with FoMO as a key factor in their choices.

Travel Behavior of Generation Z Tourists in terms of Spending Behavior

The travel behavior of Generation Z tourists in terms of spending behavior have an overall weighted mean of 4.38 and a standard deviation of 0.81 that is interpreted as "Always." This indicates that when planning a trip they consistently prioritize financial considerations. These results suggest that even how eager they travel, they do still consider their financial limits, ensuring that the expenses remain manageable. This findings aligns with recent studies of Pahlevam-Sharif et al. (2021), it is reported in their study that Gen Z tourists prefer cost-efficient options, engage in budget planning, and make spending decisions knowingly to maximize the value. The findings above reveal that this generation prioritizes travel while practicing responsible spending. In relation to their spending behavior, it was also influenced by FoMO and social media that motivate them to focus on a certain destination or experience, even if they have to be careful about how they manage other travel expenses.

Summary of Ratings on the Travel Behavior of Generation Z Tourists

The summary of the ratings on the travel behavior of Generation Z tourists shows the different levels of consistency across the three dimensions. With the spending behavior being the highest—having a weighted mean of 4.38 that is interpreted as "Always". It was presented that when young adults decide to travel they think about their budget, consider the cost, and do financial planning. It was highlighted that despite their interest in travel, they are still mindful of their expenses. Overall, these results show that people's decisions are mainly influenced by their understanding of money and how involved they are in social activities. While factors related to the destination still matter, they play a smaller role. Correspondingly, their travel behavior was influenced by the combination of their responsible spending and social engagement. Thus, it was presented that they are careful when balancing their travel intentions and limiting their budget. As well as prioritizing—having planning finances, not

only that but the feeling of FoMO caused by social media and peer behaviors also have a significant effect on their travel choices.

Multiple Regression Analysis on FoMO Sales Promotion Strategies to Travel Behavior

This section includes the multiple regression analysis that was conducted to determine how FoMO-based sales promotion strategies—discounts, coupons, and buy-one-take-one offers affect the travel behavior of Generation Z. In line with the study's Statement of the Problem 5, the analysis examines the influence of these promotional strategies on their travel frequency, destination choices, and spending behavior.

Multiple Regression Analysis with Travel Frequency as Dependent Variable

The data presents a regression analysis on how FoMO-based promotions—Discounts, Coupons, and Buy-1-Get-1-Free (B1G1F) affect the travel frequency of Generation Z tourists. The results show that the only one who predicts the travel frequency of the young adult tourist is the Discounts ($B = .207$, $\beta = .259$, $p = .007$). These results suggest that the stronger discount promotions will lead to their more

frequent travel that was driven by FoMO. In contrast to this, it is shown that the Coupons ($p = .356$) and B1G1F ($p = .125$) promotional strategies did not significantly impact their travel frequency. While these strategies attract attention, they do not strongly influence the actual travel behavior for this demographic. These results above are aligned with the existing literature, which highlights the discounts as one of the strongest motivators in consumer decision-making. According to the study of Prasad et al.(2020), they highlight how the discounts are more effective in motivating them to act quickly because they provide a clear and direct economic benefit. Similarly, studies on FoMO-driven consumption emphasize that they tend to respond more strongly to promotions that create both urgency and financial advantage (Abel et al., 2016; Stead & Bibby, 2017). This results proves that Gen Z are responsive to discounts, as they are drawn to offers that are focused on value. Additionally, if they feel like they are missing out, this will lead them to take actions—especially when there's a limited-time deal they could miss. On the other hand, both the Coupons and B1G1F promotions did not have a strong impact—likely because they involve extra steps or

conditions. These conditions make them less appealing to tourists. In short, discount promotion strategies are the most effective way to increase the travel frequency among Gen Z tourists, while those promotions that require more effort have a weaker effect on them.

Multiple Regression Analysis with Destination Choices as Dependent Variable.

The data shows the multiple regression analysis examining the influence of FoMO-based sales promotion strategies such as Discounts, Coupons, and Buy-One-Get-One-Free on the destination choices of Gen Z tourists. The findings revealed that B-O-G-O are the only factors that influence the destination choice of Gen Z ($B = .187$, $\beta = .234$, $p = .010$). This suggests that they are more likely to choose a destination that offers B-1-G-1 deals, as these promotion tactics provide an extra value. On the other hand, Discounts ($p = .139$) and Coupons ($p = .689$) do not significantly affect Gen Z's destination preferences. Although these offer additional value, they are not strong enough to shape

Gen Z's destination choice. The results show the significant effect of B-1-G-1 that aligns with past study that suggests Gen Z customers are drawn to promotions that enhance firsthand experience on their purchases (Priporas et al., 2017). B-1-G-1 offers a "value multiplier", making the experiences rewarding and inclusive, especially when the travel plan involves a group of people. This supports the studies where Gen Z are motivated by the opportunities that share experience and maximize the benefit during the travel (Fromm & Read, 2018). The insignificant effect of discounts and coupons shows In the earlier findings that some price-focused promotions may not work and be uninfluential for destination selection unless it shows unique features of the destination itself (Laran & Tsiros, 2013). Overall, it shows that BIG1F are important promotion tools in influencing Generation Z to choose a destination. This means that travel marketers who want to affect destination choice should focus on enhancing their promotions and travel experiences, like BIG1F deals. The results indicate that BIG1F offers are significant in influencing Gen Z to choose a destination.

Multiple Regression Analysis with Spending Behavior as Dependent Variable

The data presents a regression analysis that examines the impact of FoMO-based sales promotions such as Discounts, Coupons, and Buy-1-Get-1-Free (B1G1F) on the Generation Z tourists' spending behavior. The results show that Discounts have a significant positive effect ($B = .225$, $\beta = .290$, $p = .003$). Hence, they are more likely to increase their spending when discounts are offered to them. Moreover, this backs up the previous study that suggests that Gen Z's are responsive to incentives that give them an immediate value and reduced risk (Smith, 2019). On the other hand, Coupons ($p = .478$) and the B1G1F ($p = .091$) promotions do not really influence their spending, meaning that these FoMO based tactics are less convenient and appealing than those with straightforward price reduction. The study of Naeem (2021), supports the claim that coupon promotions are not effective among the Gen Z consumers who prefer instant rewards over conditional offers. Similarly, the B-1-G-1F promotions have no significant effect although they may influence their destination choices, they don't necessarily influence higher spending. All in all, the findings discovered that discounts are the most

effective FoMO based sales promotion strategy on boosting Gen Z's spending. Therefore, emphasizing the importance of immediate price reduction in shaping their financial decisions.

Multiple Regression Analysis on Level of Engagement to Travel Behavior

This section presents the multiple regression analysis that was used to determine how the FoMO-based sales promotion strategies like the discounts, coupons, and buy-one-take-one offers affects the travel behavior of Generation Z tourists . In line with the study's Statement of the Problem 6—the analysis examines the influence of these FoMO drivers on their travel frequency, destination choices, and spending behavior.

Multiple Regression Analysis with Travel Frequency as Dependent Variable

This data shows that two FoMO drivers such as Social Media Engagement ($\beta = .260$, $p = .021$) and Trend Awareness ($\beta = .211$, $p = .041$) significantly predict Gen Z's travel frequency. The active engagement with travel content online and the awareness of new travel trends increase their travel

frequency. However, Peer Influence ($\beta = .079$, $p = .474$) and the Desire for Unique Experiences ($\beta = .107$, $p = .303$) does not significantly predict travel frequency. Therefore, digital exposure and trend awareness are stronger drivers than the interpersonal pressure or their pursuit of uniqueness. Correspondingly, these motivations remain important to their mindset, the results imply that they do not independently drive how frequently they travel when considered alongside the other FoMO drivers. It appears that the digital exposure and trend sensitivity are stronger determinants than the interpersonal pressure or their pursuit of uniqueness in shaping travel frequency.

These findings support the previous research that shows how digital engagement and trend awareness determine Gen Z's travel behavior. Social media engagement, especially with visually appealing content and influencer posts, has been linked to more travel, as it sparks interest in their trips (Alhabash & Ma, 2020). Similarly, they are highly influenced by the emerging travel trends and viral content, which shape both their travel choices and how often they travel (Goh & Okumus, 2020). On the other hand,

peer influence mainly affects the destination choice or travel satisfaction, it does not affect the travel frequency, this explains why it had no significant impact in this study.

Multiple Regression Analysis with Destination Choices as Dependent Variable

This data shows that only Trend Awareness ($\beta = .414$, $p < .001$) have significantly influenced Gen Z's destination choices. This shows how they are more likely to choose a popular social media destination. Furthermore, Social Media Engagement ($\beta = .100$, $p = .337$) and Peer Influence ($\beta = .047$, $p = .692$) does not significantly predict destination choices. Although social media provides inspiration, it does not directly determine destination choices once trend awareness is considered. Similarly, Desire for Unique Experiences ($\beta = .020$, $p = .835$) does not have a significant impact.

The strong influence of trend awareness aligns with the research that shows how often they base their travel decisions on what's trending. In addition, a previous study of Alhabash & Ma (2020) shows that while social media exposure does spark

travel interest, it does not always predict their destination choices. This accounts for the claim that there is no significant result for social media engagement in this study.

Multiple Regression Analysis with Spending Behavior as Dependent Variable

The data presents the multiple regression analysis examining how the four FoMO-driven engagement factors—Social Media Engagement, Peer Influence, Trend Awareness, and Desire for Unique Experiences—influence the spending behavior of Generation Z tourists. The results indicate that none of the predictors significantly influence spending behavior, as all p-values exceed the .05 threshold. Social Media Engagement shows a marginal effect ($\beta = .231$, $p = .057$), it doesn't have statistical significance. Peer Influence ($\beta = .008$, $p = .948$) has almost no effect on how much Gen Z tourists spend. Similarly, spending behavior is not predicted by Trend Awareness ($\beta = -.051$, $p = .646$) or Desire for Unique Experiences ($\beta = -.110$, $p = .329$). Overall, it indicates that FoMO-driven engagement does—not significantly determine how much Gen Z spends during their travel, supporting the idea that spending

behavior is guided more by their personal budgets and financial priorities rather than when they experience psychological pressures or social motivations. The findings show that their travel spending is influenced more by personal budgets and spending habits rather than by FoMO related factors. Correspondingly, it is suggested that the tourism businesses must focus on providing affordable but authentic experiences and personalized options, since when it comes to travel spending Gen Z prefers value over social pressures or trends.

Summary of Findings

This section presents the important findings of the study as they connect directly to each statement of the problem.

1. The majority of respondents are Gen Z students with a balanced gender representation and diverse academic backgrounds. Their recent travel decisions present a variety of choices, showing differences in travel exposure, preferences, and planning behavior.
 2. FoMO-based promotions strategies are often appreciated by Gen Z respondents. They
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prefer immediate and high-value promotions, as determined that Discounts and BIG1F promos typically generate higher engagement compared to coupon-based promotions.

3. The findings indicate that Gen Z tourists have a moderate level of engagement regarding FoMO. Their travel interest is motivated by social media cues, peer pressure, and trend awareness. The desire for unique experiences of individuals differs, revealing their sensitivity to FoMO triggers.
4. Gen Z respondents are known to travel frequently. They express a travel behavior that is influenced by both personal and social factors, as viewed in their travel frequency, destination choice, and spending behavior, that shows a mix of social influence, convenience, and practicality.
5. Regression analysis indicates that few FoMO-based promotions have a huge impact on the travel behavior of Gen Z. However, the level of this effect varies depending on travel frequency, destination choice, and spending behavior of

respondents, revealing that some promotional strategies have more influence than others.

6. The findings reveal that FoMO drivers, specifically social media engagement and trend awareness, have a significant effect on the travel behavior of Gen Zs. Given that their influence is not consistent across all behavioral characteristics, these drivers have an impact on travel frequency, destination choice, and underlying travel motivations.

Conclusions

Based on the analysis presented in the previous chapter, some conclusions were formed about how FoMO influences the travel behavior of Gen Z tourists, specifically in terms of motivations, destination choices, spending behavior, and dependability to promotional strategies. These conclusions acknowledge the limitations of the study and potential biases that might affect how the findings are interpreted, but also highlight the key insights gained from the study.

1. The study concludes that the respondents are—typical Gen Zs with various
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academic backgrounds and different levels of travel experiences. Their demographic profile indicates that travel behavior and FoMO responses may affect age-related preferences and social influences. However, the results may not accurately represent their larger population, since the sample was limited from one university only, which is Bulacan State University- Main Campus, that affects the generalizability of the findings.

2. FoMO-based sales promotion strategies are mostly effective for Gen Z tourists, with Discounts and Buy-One-Get-One-Free promotions being the most appealing. This suggests that Gen Z responds more to immediate and high reward promotions than coupon based promos, since these strategies build a strong feeling and perceived value. Still, the survey's self reported form suggests the possibility of response bias, which could influence how strongly respondents felt or expressed their reactions to promotion.

3. Gen Z are experiencing moderate FoMO, which is commonly triggered by social media exposure, peer dynamics, and trends. While these factors influence travel interest, the desire for unique experiences differs, indicating that FoMO sensitivity is present but not universally intense among Gen Zs. Due to the study's cross-sectional design, situational or emotional factors may potentially have an effect on this variation.

4. The study's findings conclude that Gen Z tourists show active and socially influenced travel behavior. The decisions they make for travel frequency, destination choice, and spending demonstrate a balance of personal preference, peer recommendation and practical financial constraints. Still, these results could not accurately change behaviors and FoMO response as time passed since behavior is examined at a single point in time.

5. FoMO-based sales promotions strongly influence the travel behavior of Gen Z, though the influence differs depending on

the aspect of travel. Discounts and B1G1F deals have a big influence on travel decisions, while others have less of an effect. However, unmeasured factors like current financial conditions or individual personality traits may also affect how strongly promotions influence behavior.

6. FoMO drivers which include social media influence and trend awareness have significant effects on travel behavior, although their effects are concentrated, influencing specific behavioral factors more strongly than others. Knowing that these drivers were assessed through self-report, the result may be subject to recall bias or personal interpretation.

In general, FoMO plays a significant effect that shapes the travel behavior of Generation Z, these conclusions should be interpreted in light of the study's limitations including sample restrictions, self-reported data, and the cross-sectional design which may affect the strength, depth, and generalizability of the findings.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion taken from the study. The following recommendations are suggested to address each Statement of the Problem. These suggestions aim to enhance FoMO-based promotional strategies, to strengthen the engagement approaches, and have better travel experiences among Gen Z tourists.

1. Given that Gen Z tourists came from different courses and decision-making behaviors, the business and tourism industry should design a segment that has promotional content that aligns and piques their interest. Marketing segments may specialize by age group and decision-making behaviors, ensuring that promotional materials remain relevant and familiar for different subgroups within Gen Z.
 2. Given that discounts and Buy-one-get-one-free offers shown to be the most appealing marketing strategies, businesses should put focus on using these as their marketing campaigns. Promotions should show clear time limits and be shared across different platforms frequently known by Gen Z's to maximize promotional engagement and booking intentions.
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Coupons still might be used but should be redesigned to appear more special and have time-sensitivity to strengthen their impact.

3. As Gen Z as the respondents, they vary from FoMO-based across social media engagement, peer influence, trend awareness, and desire for unique experiences. Travel companies should put on careful consideration on selecting contents that taps into a motivation to travel. This includes leveraging social proof, showcasing a trend or unique travel experiences and also collaborating with influencers that are known to Gen Z.
4. With spending considerations and travel partners influencing young tourist travel decisions, institutions and travel providers should create budget-friendly packages and group travel discounts. Providing more clear cost breakdown, accommodations details and real-life feedback that can further strengthen Gen Z tourist motivations in choosing a destination with confidence.
5. Since FoMO-based promotional strategies has a significant affect into the travel

behavior outcomes, travel companies should use data about FoMO-based promotional strategies, focusing on time sensitivity offers, appealing social media advertisement, and hassle-free booking that ensures that FoMO effectively appeals to the actual travel decisions

6. Given that some FoMO drivers, particularly social media influence and trend awareness motivations have a significant influence on Gen Z travel behavior, tourism organizations should enhance and give focus on their digital presence and approaches. Featuring slices of life experiences, customer content, highlighting trending destinations and activities that offer a platform for tourists to share their experiences that can further improve the engagement and positively shape Gen Z's travel decisions.
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